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KALIT SO'ZLAR

Texnologik ta'lim, axborot ta'lim muhiti, kasbiy faoliyat, axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari (AKT), kompyuter.

The comprehensive reforms being carried out in the education system of the country are aimed at ensuring a high level of quality of education. acquisition of skills and abilities, as well as scientific research of innovative information-didactic forms of education. This, in turn, requires a radical reform of the education system, as a perfect education system plays a crucial role in educating young people to be creative, independent in all respects, which will determine the future intellectual potential and development of the republic. Today, research is being conducted in the education system of the country to improve the education system based on innovative

DEVELOPING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION TEACHERS IN AN INFORMED LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

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ANNOTATSIYA

Axborot muhitida texnologiya ta'lim o'qituvchisini kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorlashga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning ahamiyati muhokama qilinadi.

technologies, strengthen its national base, bring the training of socially active and qualified competitive personnel to world standards. Quality changes and high efficiency in education depend on their compatibility with global educational requirements and the extent to which the competencies that educators acquire in their future careers are put into practice. As a result of qualitative changes in education and high efficiency, the introduction of positive innovations in this area will ensure the quality and effectiveness of education and create a process of pedagogical innovation. Pedagogical innovation is a process that

prepares future professionals to work in a new environment, which is based on previous knowledge, a qualitative change in education and a new approach to achieving high efficiency.

The rapid penetration and improvement of information and communication technologies in the education system necessitates the creation and implementation of electronic didactic tools in the educational process. That is why information and communication technologies, as one of the advanced trends in scientific and technological development, cover many aspects of modern society.

Information is an important tool for the development of professional activity and the basis for its development. Providing professional information with new information technologies plays an important role in meeting people's need for a variety of information.

Because of information, theory combines with practice. Practice does not exist without theory, and theory does not exist or develop without practice. Today, the complex of information in various forms of society is wide and developed, and its role in professional activities is innumerable. He has several interpretations. Information is a necessary tool for development. Information is a set of scientific and technical data, knowledge about the results of the development of science and technology. In other words, information, according to this interpretation, scientific and technical activity is a product and "raw material" of the information service system.

Information is a set of products that form the basis of scientific and technical

activities and training in various fields in information service systems.

Today, the e-learning environment in the teaching of technology in any educational process includes:

- a telecommunications software environment that provides the educational process, its information and documents on the Internet to any educational institution, regardless of their professional skills and level of education.

- understands the interactions used to acquire knowledge in a digital system through an online computer.

- a telecommunications software environment that provides the educational process, its information and documents on the Internet to any educational institution, regardless of their professional skills and level of education.

- Independent work with electronic materials using a personal computer, PDA, mobile phone, DVD player, television and other electronic materials;

- Opportunity to consult, evaluate, work remotely from a remote (regional) expert (teacher);

Creating a distributed community of users (social networks) to lead shared virtual learning activities;

The education system, despite being the most conservative system, has its own characteristics in the process of transition to an informed society:

- Individualization of the educational process with the help of information technology;

- Diversification of the standard learning process;

- Development of a system of flexible individual training programs;

- Decentralization of educational institutions: home schooling, organization of various study groups;
- Informatization of educational institution management: provision of educational institutions with information systems, automation of management activities, creation and use of databases on various subject areas.

The qualitative and quantitative level of the education system allows us to think about the level of information in the country. One of the most pressing issues facing the modern education system is the involvement of everyone in it. This problem has economic, social and technological aspects. One of the challenges facing the modern information society is to involve all members of society in the system of continuing education. Due to the ever-changing nature of society, everyone is required to receive continuous education, not to lag behind the times, to change professions, to take their place in the social system. New methods of teaching, especially distance and multimedia, are becoming increasingly important. Information technology allows

people living in remote areas of the country to access specialized educational resources that are not available in their communities. In a developed information society, information superhighways technically realize this potential. Experience has shown that the use of multimedia in the education system has significantly increased the effectiveness of education. Along with the hypertext structure of the educational material, multimedia technologies allow to create highly effective teaching aids. These are e-books, multimedia encyclopedias, computer movies, databases. In an informed society, the school may be partially or completely detached from the traditional classroom system. This will create all the conditions for the organization of a full education system for the disabled. However, the Director-General of UNESCO, F. Mayor, stated: "Technology is evolving faster than it can be used in education." the relevance of the idea remains to this day. We can take some of the events mentioned above as trends in the developed information society.

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